

Individual Analysis Reflective Report

Before experience

With only a handful of work experiences, I feel that I am not prepared enough to enter the workforce as a full-time, nor do I have the capability to be committed to a certain job. Based on my previous work experience, I am easily demotivated, and I certainly am prone to experiencing job burnout, despite receiving frequent recognition from one of my employers. This is when I realised that I have not acquired the proper mindset to be fully committed to my work and to stay motivated. Therefore, I decided to pursue a master's degree to gain more insights into how management works, and I believe that by putting more effort, a rewarding outcome can be obtained from this decision. Furthermore, according to Musa and Idris (2020), job seekers today are viewed as unprepared with low endurance. Hence, learning the management styles and skills might give me some knowledge on what are the skills that I need to acquire and polish beforehand. I am hoping that through the courses I take under Master in Management will help in guiding and preparing myself for the future.

In this module, it teaches me to be more independent in carrying out my tasks. It is obvious that nothing comes easy without any effort and proper preparation. For one, it is important to be organised and updated with the deadlines being set.

When doing the individual research project, there were five stages delineated by our lecturer on how we should carry out our research project, which was useful to track my progress at certain points. Because of my past working experience and feedback from my former colleagues, I already had a specific topic that I wanted to delve into. What I did first was to come up with a research topic, and only after that, I did preliminary research. Since the beginning, I was determined to conduct research on a particular topic, and I had also thought of the potential organisation that I wanted to carry out a study on.

During experience

The initial project goal was to find out the effects of commission-based jobs on individual differences, linking employee motivation and sales performance. However, I have decided to switch the dependent variable and changed it to finding the effects of commission-based jobs on employee motivation and by relating it to individual differences and how it can affect sales performance. This decision was made after doing a preliminary data gathering. I planned to conduct a field study in one of the companies in Brunei that pay their employees based on straight commission. Despite doing research beforehand, I was too fixated on finding the effects of straight commission on employees without being truly aware that there would be a very limited study done on this topic. I was thinking of carrying out the data collection first so that based on the findings I have obtained can be used to do further secondary research to support my statements. I have presented my proposal to one of the company representatives, and at the same time, I have also outlined the research design on the sample size, when and how I should carry

out the data collection, what are the ethical considerations, and so on. But this plan backfired when we were not granted permission to conduct a field study and to rely on secondary data only, presumably because of the current pandemic.

Therefore, I had to proceed with my research by doing a systematic literature review. My topic may be relevant to some of the working population in Brunei, but I found that sticking to my topic would not be feasible. It was either due to the fact that this particular area is not widely explored by researchers or because of the limited access to published journals and articles while relying on electronic databases only. Consequently, a minor adjustment had to be made on the research topic once again with only a few weeks remaining until the deadline of this project assignment. Rather than having 'commission-based jobs' as my independent variable, I have changed it to 'compensation plans' instead as most of the databases yielded a lot of articles covering this scope of area.

Based on my personal experience when working on this paper, whilst I was emphasising on how important it is for employees to be highly motivated throughout my paper, I realised that to be constantly motivated is impossible. In the beginning, my intrinsic motivation was what drove me to be truly invested in this research, but the motivation seemed to have dissipated over time when there was a change in the mode of data collection. According to Ariani (2017), motivation is one of the crucial psychological concepts in education. Time management and motivation become even more important especially after the mid-semester break because there was so much to do all at once where assignments kept piling up with so many deadlines to meet. Being unable to effectively make use of the time often results in the inability to decide quickly and mental conflict (Besong, 2015). Eventually, meeting the goal and deadlines were the only things that mattered the most, without acknowledging the quality of the assignment content.

While in search of related articles with my topic, my frustration was just constantly building up. I have underestimated the difficulties in writing a systematic literature review by leaving the task with only a week remaining before the deadline assuming that I already had sufficient materials prepared beforehand. Even when I had a clear vision of where I planned to head with my research, carrying them out was a whole different case. It was the expectation versus reality moment for me. I was indecisive throughout the writing process because of the limited information that I had in hand. Having to focus on certain countries even complicates the situation even more, as some of the studies that are very well written with helpful information did not state where the study was conducted. This is why setting SMART goals from the beginning is highly recommended. SMART stands for specific, measurable, attainable, relevant and timely and these characteristics are defined by Schermerhorn and Bachrach (2015) as to set a clear, meaningful and relevant goal that is achievable within a certain period, especially when there is a deadline to meet.

Furthermore, amidst the writing process, we were asked to submit our progress and draft with the expectation of constructive feedback will be given so that this can aid me on how I should carry on with my research even further. Unfortunately, there was not any. Understandably enough and based on firsthand experience, people were probably preoccupied with their work to critically pay attention to others'.

Going through the articles was quite a lengthy process too. I had to fully grasp the concept before I could summarise them in my own words. Another challenging task was to paraphrase the findings into my own words without changing the meaning. The ethical dilemma that I faced was what if the idea that I presented was not the actual intention of the authors because of my different understanding. Moreover, most of my literature findings were presented with statistical analysis, one of which is not my forte.

I would say that my ideas are 75% realised, but it is not there just yet because of the limited access to relevant information. Because of this, I am not fully satisfied with the outcome of my literature review. I could have done better if only I could manage my time and structure my thoughts carefully. One problem that I find in my paper is that my findings were not critically evaluated. I was overwhelmed with so much information that I was not able to construct a proper evaluation and I have only touched what can be seen on the surface rather than diving deeper into the matter. My research paper was also lacking in applying related theories that I have covered throughout the semester to the findings. Despite this, in the end, I was still able to answer three out of the four research questions that I presented in my project assignment based on the findings that I obtained. It would have been more satisfying if I was able to answer them based on my firsthand findings since the secondary data were conducted outside of Brunei and may not be applicable in the context of Brunei.

Since my study focuses on compensation plans, I find that my definition of compensation plans was not clear per se in a way that I did not specifically state which one I wanted to focus more, either in terms of the salary or the rewards. However, oftentimes, researchers did not specify the type of compensation plans of whether their participants are being paid with a straight commission or a combination of salary and commission. This is probably why I was having difficulties to specify exactly which one I wanted to focus more into; salaries, wages or rewards. Apart from that, I am also fully aware that the compensation systems may vary in every country, with their minimum wage and so on, of which I should have brought up in my paper as well.

Additionally, when I was talking about the individual differences under the literature review, it was only covered briefly with an insufficient explanation I feel like. Firstly, I did not exactly define individual differences. Next, I have brought up about selecting the right salespeople could

help maximise the sales growth, I could have elaborated further what did I mean by the *right* salespeople and what personality traits do these *right* salespeople should have.

One of the successes that I should highlight was the ability to complete the research project on time despite the hurdles before and during the actual research being carried out. I have also learnt new information regarding salesforce control systems, different customer orientations and the lone wolf tendencies. I have successfully looked into the different types of compensation and how they can influence sales performance differently.

The thing that I would do differently next time is that I should not leave my assignment unfinished halfway through and untouched for weeks in the attempt to prioritise other tasks with closer deadlines as this has affected the writing momentum. The ideas that I initially brought up did not seem to match the ideas that I had while doing the final half of the assignment, thus for my paper to be coherent, there were a lot of changes had to be done at the very last minute.

Completion of experience

I cannot emphasise enough on how important it is to stay disciplined. Having mere interest and determination to carry out the research plan was not enough, especially when I needed reliable sources to support or even contradict my statements. When my expectation in conducting the research was not met due to the lack of information has significantly affected my motivation and work performance. There are still so many improvements to be made in terms of research skills, including the skills involving interpreting statistical analysis and to have better time management. The lack of time management skills is one of the main contributing factors that have caused my indecisiveness and unsatisfactory outcome.

This reflective report has made me fully aware of what I am lacking in and in what aspect that I should put more focus into. What I realised was that putting more efforts alone is not enough. By putting more effort will require *more* effort and it was not easy to stay committed, especially when one is experiencing academic burnout. I should have considered my mental well-being as well as how far I will be able to cope with the stress and heavy workload within a short time. When comparing my journey in doing a master's degree with my undergraduate journey, the latter was just a walk in the park. However, this has helped me to build more endurance and not to give up on my tasks prematurely. I am for one glad that I decided to pursue a master's degree because of the knowledge that I have gained so far in just fourteen weeks.

Group Assignment Reflective Report

Before experience

Whilst there were so many hurdles that I had to undergo during my individual research project, the group case study was bearable. Our project goal was to investigate the training and motivation practices in two slaughterhouses and determine the impact they have on the performance and task efficiency among the employees. Before proceeding with the study, the group members had brainstormed together via online on which slaughterhouses that we can conduct our research on while considering the feasibility in gaining access to the slaughterhouse.

During experience

We managed to collect primary data by interviewing two owners of the slaughterhouses. My group members and I had the opportunity to visit one of the slaughterhouses twice to conduct interviews with the owner and the employees. During the first interview session, only one of my group members and I were able to go to the site. While my partner was in charge of interviewing the owner, I had taken the role of jotting down the important notes. At the same time, I had also partaken in asking some questions whenever I needed some clarifications on the statement that the owner has made.

During the second interview session, I had the chance to interview one of the employees. It was quite a humbling experience to hear what the employee has gone through prior to and during working at the slaughterhouse. Since the interview was a semi-structured one where most questions were constructed on the spot, when we were structuring our written report, there were some questions that I wish I had asked. There was a sense of regret but unfortunately, nothing could be done about it because of the time constraint.

When conducting an online interview with one of the owners, my group members and I each took turns in asking questions to the owners since it took him a while to respond to our questions. This was one of the challenging moments that we had encountered when carrying out the data collection. It was not only time-consuming, but it was also demotivating at some point because we had to wait for his responses and this online interview took us about three hours.

Throughout the data collection process, I had willingly participated in all the interview sessions and the discussions with my group members as I should be. Being a good team player is crucial to achieve the goal of our study and to ease the overall process. I had also actively contributed to the Literature Review Table and the Teaching and Research Notes. One of the tasks that I can take full credit of is in writing the profiles of the owners. Since everyone has their own priorities, I always made sure that I completed my part early so that should there be any changes needed to be done, we still have plenty of time to spare.

In my opinion, this was thus far a group with great teamwork that I ever worked with throughout my university journey where each of us has contributed to the group work equally and were punctual when it comes to contributing their ideas into the written tasks. During the writing process, the introduction, literature review, and methodology were written at our own different time, but we had made sure that the three of us were present when writing the results and discussions along with the conclusion. It was truly a satisfying sight to see that we have managed to complete our group assignment two days before the deadline of the report. When there were instances that I disagree with certain points that my group members had made, I tend to provide with an alternative point rather than disagreeing blindly. Additionally, rather than constructing imperative sentences that sound like a command during discussions, I always made the habit of forming interrogative sentences to soften the way I voiced out my opinion.

I noticed that our agreeableness and good communication were the keys to successful group work. As asserted by Graziano et al. (1996), agreeable encourage others to contribute and are supportive of everyone's different perspectives and help to create a comfortable environment to share information.

Completion of experience

From this group work, I realised that my strengths are having the ability to summarise certain information with ease and sticking to our personal deadlines. I learnt that the people that I am surrounded with can have an impact on the outcome of my work performance where I was constantly motivated to partake in any group discussions. This can be said that I can be a good team player whenever I need to, which is one of the essential attributes in the workplace (Knippen & Green, 1999). My weaknesses and the skill areas that I still need to develop are my critical thinking skills and the ability to apply related theories into certain findings. Finally, I certainly cannot take full credit of our group work achievements as I feel that my group members have contributed equally, if not, even more than I did. There is nothing that I would do differently next time apart from constructing much better interview questions that allow us to obtain richer findings and more to analyse from.

(2,866 words)

References

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